

RESEARCHERS JUST LOVE HIGH IMPACT JOURNALS, BUT ARE THERE CAREER- PROOF ALTERNATIVES?

Our findings, SURF research day 2026

ABSTRACT

At the SURF research day 2026, we asked the attendees of our workshop if they agree or not with four statements. This report summarizes the views of the participants.

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Statement 1

Universities and funders increasingly promote responsible research assessment and ‘room for everyone’s talent’, but in practice researchers are still mainly rewarded for publishing in high impact journals.

The statement resonated with most participants; only two audience members disagreed. Those participants noted that **NWO and some universities implement narrative CVs**. However, they argued that many researchers don’t take advantage of this system yet. **“Unfortunately, right now it feels like an additional burden to also generate additional non-traditional output next to traditional output. It is becoming an extra thing you need to do on top of all the other things.”**

A participant from **a university of applied sciences (HBO)** offered a different perspective. **In some disciplines, journal impact factors are not used**; therefore, this statement does not apply. In this context, doing other things than publishing" papers (which is not a requirement for finalizing the PhD), it is perceived as normal. “It is expected that you will do less research as you are doing other things”.

Statement 2

Diamond Open Access may be a fairer and more inclusive publishing model, but most researchers still do not see it as a viable option for advancing their careers.

The participants felt that these were two different statements and were divided into two.

Statement 2.1

Diamond Open Access is a fairer and more inclusive publishing model.

The attendees agreed with this except few which thought that **someone still needs to pay for it. Concerns about the long term preservation and availability of the articles and how sustainable this model is was brought forward. For** this is important to have a trusted institution which will support the infrastructure. Journal continuity needs to be there; journals are a community.

Statement 2.2

Most researchers still do not see Diamond OA as a viable option for advancing their careers.

The audience sees **Diamond OA as an option, but it depends on the prestige of the journals.** The **university of applied sciences can again serve a role model,** as many **do not attach recognition and rewards to the status and impact.** What is more important is that the research output is open access.

Statement 3

Even if preprints and open peer review can improve scholarly communication, most researchers still do not trust them enough to use them as part of their regular publishing practices.

The audience was **divided** as half them found that the main problem is that the **awareness level of preprints and open peer review is really low**. Much of the research staff and library staff need to explain these concepts to them. One of the **concerns of the researchers is that they are afraid to get scooped when sharing output in an earlier stage**. **Explaining the (dis) advantages better will help to create trust in them. One good way to do this is via ambassadors.**

One of the concerns with the **open peer review is that the people themselves cannot judge the quality of the review**. (e.g. what if non-experts review it?). Is there a way to gate-keep this? What if a non-reviewed, flawed AI-generated article gets attention? We could look back at the COVID pandemic time and see how fast science was disseminated but also misinterpreted.

Statement 4

Real change in scholarly publishing will only happen if universities, funders, and evaluation systems change the incentives researchers are judged by.

The **audience remained divided**. Some argued that **research communities are the primary drivers of change and that substantial supporting structures are needed to achieve a genuine shift in culture**. Simply changing the rules will not be sufficient, nor will change occur overnight; **cultural transformation will not happen overnight, but it is a gradual process**.

Many researchers who are in committees have been selected based on impact factors, so they still chose and reward in the same way.

“We are good at training people to attract funding; if you change the funding rules, the rest will follow.”